

Thriving or struggling in academia?: Assessing the (Contextual Antecedents of) Mental Well-Being of Researchers in Higher Education in Montenegro

Sabina Osmanovic
University of Montenegro
Stefan T. Mol
University of Amsterdam
Ivana Petrovic
University of Belgrade
Jana Lasser
Graz University of Technology
Sofija Pajic
Radboud University Nijmegen
Igor Portoghese
University of Cagliari
Carla van der Voort

Indicate your track:

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1. Scientific and practitioners' research presentations
 1. Bottom-up and community-driven interventions
 2. Institutional interventions and policies
 3. Policy-Level insights
2. Workshop/hands-on practices for enhancing researcher mental health and well-being

Purpose

The main purpose of this mixed methods study is to identify not only personal but also contextual facilitators and inhibitors of researcher mental health at two Higher Education institutions in Montenegro as well as to identify their impact on sustainable research careers. In addition, this study is intended to serve as a pilot/baseline study for the much larger international ReMO Mental Health Survey, that is being prepared by the ReMO Survey SIG. To date few studies have been carried out specifically on the role of context in shaping mental health, emphasizing the significance and necessity of conducting this particular research.

Design

This pilot study aims to collect data at two universities in Montenegro to identify the main challenges researchers are facing in the ‘dynamic’ environment of academia. A pilot online survey will be conducted at different faculties and departments within the two universities to investigate how interfaculty and interdepartmental differences relate to individual level mental health, and how mental health in turn relates to the sustainability of research careers. By surveying two different universities (public and private), the collected data will be compared to gain insights into the characteristics of mental health in these two institutions as well as their “best practices” in supporting the well-being of researchers. Furthermore, the study aims to establish whether, and if so how, the well-being of researchers is impacted at the faculty and departmental level, and to derive evidence-based policy recommendations.

Results (if applicable)

In addition to providing data on the state of the perceived level of mental health, and antecedents thereof, in the two universities in Montenegro, the reported findings of this pilot study will be useful to the institutions to identify the key difficulties researchers encounter during their academic careers and how that might affect their mental health. This will enable the institutions to develop/improve strategies to foster healthy workplaces and raise awareness of the importance of researcher mental health as well as setting effective support services. Next to that, this study will draw from and contribute to the ongoing work of the Survey SIG, examining/piloting questions pertaining to i) survey administration, appropriate survey length, ethical/privacy issues, translation issues, appropriate dissemination channels and so forth. Initial data analysis is expected to be completed by the time of the ReMO conference.

Implications

Considering the sensitivity of the topic, obstacles may be encountered at the level of the management who might be reluctant to respond to the survey. Being unique, this study will set a basis for further research opportunities and policymaking. By generating and disseminating a pilot survey, we will be able to create and apply a model which will primarily be of use to the ReMo Survey SIG in preparing a larger-scale survey to be conducted in multiple Higher Education institutions across Europe.